

Modified Symmetric Three-stage Doherty Power Amplifier for 5G

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Abstract— This paper presents an advanced three-stage Doherty amplifier (DPA), using three 10W packaged GaN-HEMT devices from CREE. The amplifier incorporates three quarter-wave impedance transformers in the output combining circuit. The output matching networks consist of micro-strip line, lumped-parameter components and offset lines of the carrier and peaking cells that are used for proper load modulation. The transmission line in the input path of the carrier cell is inserted to adjust the delay among the carrier and peaking cells. The overall behavior of the three-stage DPA with the target of high drain efficiency at 6 and 8dB output power back-off is compared with a two-stage Doherty power amplifier and single ended power amplifier, while operating at 3.6 GHz by using Agilent's Advanced Design System simulation. The designed three-stage power amplifier exhibits a power-added efficiency (PAE) of 53.75% at full output power, and 50% at 8dB back-off. The power amplifier is capable of delivering up to 46dBm of output power.

Index Terms—Doherty power amplifier (DPA), GaN-HEMT, long-term evolution (LTE), output power capacity, three-stage DPA.

I. INTRODUCTION

In future emerging 5G mobile systems, frequency spectrum should be fully utilized in order to support multiple Gbps' of data rates. 5G will investigate new spectrally efficient transmission waveforms, but certainly OFDM type signals will still play a pivotal role in the data signaling channel due to legacy wireless systems. However, these exhibits time-varying amplitude and phase characteristics due to the large envelope fluctuation in the time domain resulting in high peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR). The adoption of high PAPR modulated signals enforces the Power Amplifier (PA) to be operated in the back-off level from its peak saturated power, resulting into poor average efficiency. Among various efficiency enhancement approaches, the conventional Doherty power amplifier (DPA) is considered as one of the promising approaches for improving efficiency over the 6-dB output power back-off [1]. However, the power usage profile shows that most of the time the power amplifier operates at average transmitted output power in the range of 9-12dB level below the maximum power, therefore, the 6 dB back-off efficiency improvement of the conventional Doherty technique is insufficient and results in poor system efficiency [2]. It is possible to use more than two amplifiers, so called "Multistage configuration", to maintain the efficiency throughout the back-off region, and extend the back-off level far beyond the classical design [3]. In the past few years, many different types of "Three-Stage" DPAs have been proposed with various advantages and improved performances. The

works of [4-6] have investigated the gate bias control, using the envelope tracking (ET) technique for enhancing the efficiency at the backed-off output power level, and the peak power at the same time by proper load modulation. The gate bias voltage of the driving amplifier is adjusted according to the input power levels in order to eliminate the gate leakage current at high input power levels. Moreover, the inverted DPA (IDPA) which has advantages of the reduced circuit size and high efficiency at the low power region has been introduced in [7]. In other work [8], the output combining techniques have been modified in order to increase the linear output power and corresponding efficiency which reduces the heat dissipation and overall energy consumption, and enables a potential low cost solution.

In this work an Advanced Design System (ADS) software has been used to design the Modified three-stage DPA with high efficiency and high linearity operates at the 3.6 GHz band frequency. 3.6 GHz was initially used by Fixed Wireless Access providers, offering WiMAX based on the increasingly obsolete IEEE802.16 standards, and will be used to help operators deploy 5G wireless technology relies on C-band spectrum to deliver the best compromise between capacity and coverage.

The results obtained will be compared with a two-way DPA and conventional power amplifier (Class B). The organization of this paper is as follows: the basic operating principle of the three-stage Doherty power amplifier is presented in section II. Doherty design methodology is introduced in section III by using the Cree's CGH40010 transistor in the 3.6 GHz band frequency available in the Agilent's ADS2016.01. Moreover, the DPA's even input power splitter used to drive three active devices, and power combiner are discussed in this section. Next, the power gain, Power Added Efficiency (PAE) and drain efficiency behavior of three-stage DPA are compared with that of two-way DPA and single PA according to simulation results. Finally, in last Section the conclusion is given.

II. DOHERTY AMPLIFIER ARCHITECTURE

The Doherty amplifier proposed by W. H. Doherty in 1936 [1] is usually implemented by a proper combination of two active devices that operate as Main and Peaking power stages. It employs an impedance inverting network to modulate the load presented to the main amplifier according to the current supplied by the peaking device, leading to efficient operation.

Most PAs have a single maximum efficiency point at the peak maximum power level due to constant load, On the other

hand, in the Doherty amplifier at low power level, only the carrier amplifier is operational and it reaches the maximum value at the back-off point as a result of using twice the optimum load value. At the Doherty region, the efficiency of the peaking device starts to increase, and the second maximum efficiency point is reached when the peaking amplifier experiences maximum voltage swing at peak power level. Therefore, it has two maximum efficiency points, and thus enhancing the efficiency at the backed-off output power level. However, a conventional two-way Doherty architecture exhibits a significant drop in efficiency in the region between the efficiency peaking points. The Multi-Stage architecture based on sequentially turning on condition of several peaking devices depicted in Fig.

1. a, provides higher efficiencies at the back-off levels in between the efficiency peaking points overcoming the significant reduction of back-off efficiency introduced by conventional Doherty PA.

Fig. 1. (a) Multistage Doherty amplifier architectures, (b) a Conventional 3-Stage Doherty Configuration.

Among the various Multi-stage Doherty PAs, the three-stage Doherty PA has a superior efficiency characteristic because it has three maximum efficiency points along the output power level. The basic three-stage Doherty power amplifier architecture shown in Fig. 1. b, uses more than one peaking amplifier, with quarter-wave transmission lines to combine their output powers [9]. It consists of a power splitter to properly divide the input signal to the device gates in three different branches, and an output power combining network including an impedance inverter, to sum in phase the signals arising from the three active devices. The characteristic impedances of each output quarter-wave transmission line depend on the levels of back-off power and can be calculated from:

$$z_{0i} = R_L \prod_{j=1}^i \frac{1}{\alpha_j} \quad (1)$$

$$\prod_{j=k}^{\frac{i+k}{2}} \alpha_{2j-k} = 10^{\frac{OBO_i}{20}} \quad (2)$$

Where $i=1,2$. $k = 1$ for $i=1$, or $k = 2$ for $i=2$. OBO_i is the back-off level from the maximum output power of the system at which the efficiency will peak. The R_L value is determined by the optimum loading condition of the second peaking stage, according to the following relationship:

$$R_L = (1 - \alpha_1) \cdot R_{opt,peaking 2} \quad (3)$$

For most practical cases of the three-stage Doherty power amplifier whose block schematic is shown in Fig. 1, the characteristic impedances of each output quarter-wave transmission line can be obtained from (4) and (5) to be,

$$z_{01} = \alpha_1 R_L \quad (4)$$

$$z_{01} = \alpha_1 \alpha_2 R_L \quad (5)$$

$$\alpha_1 = 10^{B_1/20} \quad (6)$$

$$\alpha_2 = 10^{B_2/20} \quad (7)$$

Where $B_1 = 6$ and $B_2 = 12$ dB for peak efficiencies at -6 dB and -12 dB back-off points, respectively.

The conventional three-stage Doherty is a direct extension of the two-way Doherty amplifier and behaves as a two-way Doherty up to the first back-off efficiency peak, and then from the peak to full power the main and first peaking amplifier are behaving like a main amplifier that is being load modulated by the current contribution from the second peaking amplifier. However, there are two issues associated with the conventional three-stage Doherty: firstly, different device sizes are required to provide efficiency peaks at the back-off region, which leads to added complexity; and secondly, the dynamic load modulation of the carrier amplifier stops between peak efficiency points at a certain power level, driving the main amplifier into extreme saturation leading to degradation of linearity.

III. OPERATION MECHANISM OF MODIFIED THREE-STAGE DOHERTY POWER AMPLIFIER

The Modified Three-Stage Doherty technique has been reported by NXP recently [10]. This topology schematic diagram is shown in Fig. 2: it is portrayed as a parallel combination of one carrier PA, and one Doherty PA used as a peaking PA with their outputs joined by a quarter-wave transmission line, which performs impedance transformation. This architecture utilizes identical power amplifiers having equal sizes for the main and peaking PAs which reduces development time, and delivers the three maximum efficiency points similar to a conventional three-level Doherty without degrading much average efficiency. Thus, the three peak efficiency points are formed: at the two turn-on points and at the peak power. Also, it contains phase offset lines to ensure that when the peaking amplifier is switched off, an open circuit is presented to the Doherty combiner and the minimum power is dissipated in the peaking output matching circuits.

Fig. 2. Modified 3-Stage Doherty Configuration.

Fig. 3, shows the equivalent circuit of 3-stage modified DPA replacing the main and peaking transistors with equivalent ideal current sources. The impedance seen by the main amplifier can be changed by varying the current supplied by the peaking devices, while the voltage swing across the main has to be constant to maximize the efficiency. Once the main amplifier saturates, the peaking amplifiers reduce the impedance seen at the output of the main PA by delivering current; this leads to current conduction to the load, even when the main amplifier is saturated. Thus, the load impedance of each amplifier can be derived by the active load-pulling principle.

Fig. 3. Operational diagram of the three-stage DPA.

A. Load Modulation of the Modified Three-Stage Doherty Power Amplifier

Load modulation suitable for Doherty operation can be achieved for the Doherty amplifier at three stages, and Fig. 4, illustrates its dynamic load lines with identical unit PAs. At the low power region, when only the main amplifier operates by $3R_L$ load impedance due to the quarter-wave-line impedance inverter, both peaking amplifiers are turned off with infinite load impedance.

As the input drive level increases in the middle region, the first peaking PA turned on at the first maximum efficiency point, starts to deliver current into the output load. This increases the current in the common load causes the impedance seen by the main amplifier to degrade gradually from $3R_L$ to $2R_L$ due to the action of impedance inverter. Also, the impedance of the first peaking amplifier converts from infinity to $4R_L$, leading to maintain maximum efficiency. This reduction in output impedance of the main amplifier capable it to deliver more power into the common load whilst remaining in voltage saturation. Since the main amplifier and first peaking PA are both running at voltage saturation, they both deliver maximum efficiency. The second maximum efficiency point is achieved when the output power is backed off 6 dB from the peak power.

With the input power increasing further in the high power region, the second peaking PA is switched on, and the load impedances of all PAs are inverted to R_L , and thus the peak output power is reached resulting in forming the third maximum efficiency point. Since each PA has a maximum efficiency, the three-stage Doherty PA has three maximum efficiency points as a function of input power level.

Fig. 4. Load-lines of the three-stage Doherty PA according to the input power levels. (a) Main PA. (b) Peaking PA 1. (c) Peaking PA 2.

B. Circuit prototype and results

In this paper, the bias circuit for the main amplifier is based on the class B mode where the operating point of the transistor model of CGH40010F is located exactly at the boundary between the cutoff region and the active region (at -3.1V) at the gate and datasheet recommends 28V bias voltage at drain. The two peaking amplifiers are biased on class C mode located below the threshold. To find the optimal output impedances of the transistor operating in the linear region, the load pull simulation is performed using the non-linear model of the transistor. In order to determine the optimum load that the device should see, the efficiency and output power in the operating frequency at 3.6GHz are tracked and proper impedances deliver maximum efficiency and power should be selected. In this regard, an optimum impedance for maximum efficiency at the low and middle power regions for the main branch, and the optimum impedance for maximum delivered power on the high power regime for the main and peaking PAs in the DPA must be selected.

In order to block DC, ATC 800 capacitors (800A330) and Radial stubs are used in the three-stage Doherty PA, realizing RF grounds and impedance matching circuits. It can reduce loss and reflection at high frequencies. Isolation between the DC supply and the RF path is achievable by placing near the DC supply three decoupling capacitors capable of providing a low impedance path to ground. However, the radial stub with the quarter wave line together realize an open circuit condition at the operating frequency. Within this work, the Rogers4350B substrate with dielectric constant $\epsilon_r = 3.66$ and thickness $h = 0.762$ mm is applied. In order to improve the performance of three-stage DPA, it might be necessary to design the input and output matching for main and peaking PAs slightly different, with similar principle. After optimization of the input and output matching network for the amplifiers, offset lines need to be added at the outputs to assure that the load modulation is correctly transferred.

Fig. 5, shows the equivalent circuit representation of a three-way modified Wilkinson power divider used in the Doherty design [11]. Assuming all the impedances of the input and three output ports be $R_L = 50\Omega$, the characteristic impedances of the quarter-wave transmission lines are selected for a maximally flat performance as $Z_1 = 114\Omega$ and $Z_2 = 65.8\Omega$. To match the circuit at the center frequency, the values of the ballast planar resistors should be chosen as $R_1 = 64.95\Omega$ and $R_2 = 200\Omega$. In this case, the isolation between output ports of such a three-way divider demonstrates more than 20 dB in an octave frequency bandwidth.

Fig. 5. Microstrip three-way divider.

Also, in this work, the two-way DPA (classical DPA) and conventional power amplifier type class B have been designed. A harmonic balance was performed on the design to determine the spectral content of voltages and currents in the circuit in order to measure the PAE of the amplifier in the presence of interference. The simulation results showing Gain, PAE and drain efficiency of the modified three-stage DPA are shown in Fig.6 and compared with that of B/C Doherty PA and Class B PA. The peaking PAs of the two-way and three-stage Doherty PA are turned on at one-half and one-third of the input voltage, respectively. The characteristic behavior of the 3-stage DPA is apparent from the fact that the PAE reaches an initial peak and remains high until peak power is reached.

The simulation result in Fig. 6. a, indicates a small signal transducer gain to be flat at around 15.52dB, and when the gain compression starts, the gain decreases with increasing output power. At 3.6 GHz the maximum drain efficiency of class B is 60.30% at input power of 35dBm. This implies that the amplifier enters saturation after it reaches an output power

of 40.58dBm. The Power amplifier class B indicates a PAE of 54.71% at the maximum output power of 40.12dBm, and input power of 29dBm. According to Fig. 6. b, the gain flatness of the Doherty amplifier is worse than the Single class B due to the class C bias state of the peak transistor in the Doherty amplifier, which is flat at around 12dB. On the contrary, the power-added efficiency (PAE) of the Doherty amplifier at the 6dB back-off and maximum output power of 44.15dBm point reaches 50%. Finally, the three-stage Doherty in Fig. 6. c, shows a gain flatness of around 12dB and 50% PAE at 8dB back-off from the peak output power of 46dBm and 53.75% at maximum output power.

Fig. 6. Simulation results of Gain, PAE and efficiency of Single Class B, B/C Doherty PA and Modified three-stage DPA.

Fig. 7. Impedance transformations on the Smith chart. (a) Conventional Doherty the main amplifier, blue curve: peaking amplifier, (b) Three-stage

Doherty. Red curve: the main amplifier, blue curve: peaking1 PA and purple curve: peaking2 PA.

Fig.7.a, shows the appropriate impedance transformations on Smith chart to determine the offset line lengths of main PA from maximum efficiency point to maximum output power point and peaking PA from infinity to maximum output power point for conventional Doherty PA and Fig.7.b indicates the load impedance transformation for main and two peaking PAs in three-stage Doherty PAs. The measured performances of the symmetric three-stage DPA are summarized in Table I, and compared to the previously published three-way and three-stage DPAs. Overall, the results of this work represent a good compromised between output power and power added efficiency at 3.6GHz without any further linearization method.

TABLE I. Performance Comparison

Ref.	Freq. (GHz)	Device	Back-off dB	PAE	P_{out} (dBm)	Signal
[7]	2.14	Si LDMOSFET	9	40%	40	WCDMA
[12]	2.14	LDMOS	8	45%	48.7	CDMA
[13]	3.5	GaN HEMTs	8	39.5 %	41.4	WiMAX
[14]	2.14	LDMOSFET	9.8	31%	43.4	WCDMA
[15]	2.5	GaN HEMT	8	30.4	42	WCDMA
This work	3.6	GaN HEMT	8	50%	46	WIMAX

IV. CONCLUSION

An overview on the operating principle and design approach of the Modified symmetric three-stage Doherty form NXP in order to enhance the trade-off between energy efficiency and linearity has been presented. Simulations verified that the three-stage Doherty PAs have a significant improvement in the PAE in the low power region, compared to the conventional Doherty and single-stage design. The unit PA was designed using Cree’s CGH40010 GaN HEMT device at 3.6 GHz. The DPA limitations, especially regarding device gain degradation due to the bias condition of peaking PAs with higher losses, tend to become more severe in multistage designs as the center frequency is increased. The design process in this paper can easily be generalized to the design of an N-stage Doherty amplifier that mitigates efficiency degradation up to even higher output power back-off levels.

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